

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Evaluation of Tube Screamer Simulation using Machine Learning

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July 2022

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Abstract

In this paper a comparison between the original analog circuit that represents the ground truth and the simulation of nonlinear analog circuits using neural networks is performed. Traditionally the white box approach has provided some good results in terms of accuracy but implies an important computational demand to emulate digital audio effects (DAFx). Newer approaches using neural networks provide a black box approach that can be more efficient, accessible and potentially obtain similar or even better results. In this work I build the original electronic clone analog circuit as well as the equivalent digital circuit using the state of the art technologies using neural networks and perform an evaluation methodology to obtain some insights.

Keywords: Comparison; Simulation; Analog Circuits; DAFx; White Box; Black Box; Neural Networks; Evaluation;

Chapter 1

Introduction

Traditionally audio effects have been built using analog electronic circuits capable of producing real-time nonlinear transformations to signals, including components such as diodes, transistors or triodes that produce the desired transformation. The use of Digital Audio Workstations (DAWs) for music production combined with the digital stability and ease of integration of software has promoted the use of Virtual Analog (VA) modeling which allows musicians to recreate the particular effect without investing in expensive analog equipment.

To obtain these models that emulate analog circuits the approach has been to try to generate a physical model for each component of the circuit thus producing a white-box model, approaches such as Spice or WDF have provided a solid and accurate fashion to simulate electronic analog circuits as long as the circuit components are known. Computational cost is also an important issue when emulating complex especially when a circuit includes many reactive components or nonlinear elements. In this work this approach will be considered as one important candidate when performing the comparison.

A newer approach to tackle DAFx is to use a black-box method, which consists in training a model based on the inputs and outputs signals in the original circuit and be able to replicate the observed input-output mapping effects for other signals. Different approaches to obtain this model, including WaveNet, Recurrent NN and

LSTM will be studied. Recurrent NN will be considered the candidate for black-box modeling to be compared against the white-box approach. In this work a comprehensive comparison among two different approaches, and their respective state of the art architectures, white box and black box methodologies. The comparison will be based on a real Ibanez Tube Screamer clone considered as ground truth and some objective and subjective experiments will be performed.

The Ibanez Tube Screamer is an overdrive/distortion pedal largely used in different music styles and iconic recordings, for its characteristic mids distortion and subtle effects on lows and highs. The constructed circuit consists on a nonlinearity caused by two antiparallel diodes configured in the feed forward loop of an operational amplifier, which depending on the value of a potentiometer produces distortion for a given input signal.

The work will be organized as follows, first a comprehensive state of the art of the latest technologies and architectures will be studied in chapter 2, next the methodology will be presented with the detailed procedures to obtain the needed data to perform the comparison, that will be followed by chapter 3 with the obtained results and finally in chapter 4 a discussion will be made in order to further concretize the results obtained.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

2.1 Analog Linear circuits

Electronic linear circuits obey the superposition principle, in other words the output of the circuit when a linear combination of signals $ax_1(t) + bx_2(t)$ is applied to the system the resulting signal is equal to the linear combination of the signals $x_1(t)$ and $x_2(t)$ applied separately, as seen in equation 2.1.

$$F(ax_1 + bx_2) = aF(x_1) + bF(x_2) \quad (2.1)$$

The superposition principle must be verified by both the voltage as well as the current of the system, implying the measured output magnitudes must be a linear combination of the input. An alternate definition of linearity, when the components' values of the circuit are constant and don't vary with time is that when a sinusoidal input voltage or current of frequency f is applied, the current through any component or the voltage between two points is also sinusoidal with frequency f . A linear circuit with constant component values is called linear time-invariant (LTI) [1]. Examples of linear circuits are amplifiers, differentiators, integrators, linear electronic filters, or any circuit composed exclusively of ideal resistors, capacitors, inductors, op-amps (in the "non-saturated" region), and other "linear" circuit elements.

2.2 Analog Nonlinear circuits

The circuits that I will base my study on are not linear circuits, which can be more difficult to simulate as the voltage in some components vary with the level of voltage or current in other parts of the circuit, resulting in differential equations which cannot be explicitly solved since variables are interdependent, it is usually solved iteratively or using other methods that will be explained in section 2. Some examples of nonlinear electronic components are: diodes, transistors, and iron core inductors and transformers when the core is saturated. In general, although the basic nonlinearities of these devices are quasi-static for audio frequencies, placing the statically nonlinear device into a circuit with reactive devices will produce a nonlinear ordinary differential equation. This is especially true for voltage-mode circuits, where voltage is the signal variable, as in many amplifier circuits. The nonlinearity must be solved against the constraints imposed by the circuit, always yielding an implicit expression for the transfer curve mapping input voltage to output voltage. Reactive components apply complex constraints, yielding a nonlinearity with embedded memory, or equivalently, a filter with an embedded nonlinearity [2].

2.2.1 Diode Clipper

The Diode Clipper is a nonlinear electronic wave shaping circuit that takes an input waveform and clips or cuts off its top, bottom or both together. This transformation produces an output waveform that resembles a flattened version of the input, called clipping. In electric guitar pedals is typically a first-order resistor-capacitor (RC) low-pass filter with a diode limiter across the capacitor preventing the signal from exceeding a predetermined reference voltage level as it limits the voltage excursion across the capacitor to about a diode drop (the diode "turn-on" voltage, approximately 0.7 V) in either direction around signal ground. Is the basic component used by guitar pedals to introduce distortion in the waveform and is included in the further complex guitar distortion effects that will be studied.

2.2.2 Ibanez Tube Screamer

The Ibanez Tube Screamer is one of the most well known guitar overdrive pedals. There have been several reissues of the pedal since the release of the original TS808 in the late 1970s. For this study, the TS7 version, which was introduced in the early 2000s, was used [3]. Digital models for the Tube Screamer have been previously proposed by Yeh et al. [4], Werner et al. [5], and Eichas et al. [6]. The simplified structure of the Tube Screamer pedal is shown in Figure 1. The nonlinear behaviour of the pedal occurs in the clipping amp. It is an op-amp-based bandpass filter with diodes in the feedback path of the op amp, this band pass filter characterizes the tube screamer and is due to the components at this stage. After the clipping amp, there is the tone stage, which consists of a passive lowpass filter followed by an active filter, which can act as a low-pass or a high-pass filter depending on the position of the tone potentiometer.

Figure 1: Simplified structure of the Tube Screamer pedal [3].

2.3 White Box Modelling

In a nutshell white box approaches use knowledge of a circuit's structure to derive digital models [7]. This is a useful approach when a circuit's schematic is known, which is often the case with classic audio circuits and is certainly the case when a circuit is being designed from scratch.

If a circuit is simple, it is often easy to derive its transfer function by hand using basic analysis tools from electrical engineering such as loop analysis, mesh analysis,

or node analysis. If a circuit is more complicated, it may be helpful to write out a signal flow graph of its constituent equations and solve the transfer function.

For Virtual Analog modelling of complicated and nonlinear circuits, several systematic modelling paradigms have been proposed. The most prominent is State-Space Modelling. A final approach is Wave Digital Filter modelling.

2.3.1 State Space Methods

Represents the construction of a mathematical model as a set of input, output and state variables related by first-order differential equations. This is well explained by Yeh in his paper “Digital implementation of musical distortion circuits by analysis and simulation”. The continuous time representation of this type of system is given as [8].

$$\dot{x} = Ax + Bu + Ci \quad (2.2)$$

$$i = f(v) \quad (2.3)$$

$$v = Dx + Eu + Fi \quad (2.4)$$

$$y = Lx + Mu + Ni \quad (2.5)$$

Where x is the vector of the system states, y is the output vector of the system, u represents the inputs, i includes the nonlinear effects in the dynamics of the system, v is the input vector for the nonlinear function, \dot{x} is the time derivative of x , $f(v)$ is a multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) nonlinear mapping, and A to F and L to N are the matrices mapping x , u and i to the states and the output. To be able to simulate the system, a discretization of the model is performed and the derived system in the discrete domain has the form [9]

$$x(n) = f_s H x(n-1) + H(Bu(n) + Ci(n)) \quad (2.6)$$

$$i(n) = f(v(n)) \quad (2.7)$$

$$v(n) = Dx(n-1) + Eu(n) + Fi(n) \quad (2.8)$$

$$y(n) = Lx(n-1) + Mu(n) + Ni(n) \quad (2.9)$$

$$H = (f_s I + A)^{-1}, \alpha = f_s \quad (2.10)$$

f_s is the sampling rate, H is the discrete state update matrix, and I is the identity matrix. It has been confirmed that the discretization method as well as the sampling rate are directly related to the stability of the system. This system cannot be explicitly solved, since i and v are interdependent (delay-free loop), it could be solved iteratively but this approach is avoided for real-time applications. A series of mathematical tools are explained in order to transform this iterative model into an implementable real-time system, the K method [10]. It proposes a solution for SS systems, which can be implemented in real-time (without an iterative algorithm). In order to deal with this problem, it is possible to solve the nonlinear function by decomposing into a nonlinear instantaneous multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) map $f(\cdot)$ and a linear filter $L(s)$ containing all the system dynamics. The K method aims to isolate any delay-free path connecting any element of y with any element of x . Thereafter, geometrical transformations are applied to the system in order to get rid of those paths.

2.3.2 WDF

The Wave Digital Filter concept was developed in the early 1970s by Alfred Fettweis developed as a way of designing special digital filters with the same structure as certain analog prototypes [7]. These structures rendered the behaviour of those analog reference filters robust against electrical component variation. In this particular approach, waves represent the variables as their signal variables which leads to excellent tolerance characteristics. Their frequency responses are insensitive to coefficient truncation and roundoff accumulation (especially compared to, for instance, a direct-form realisation of their continuous-time transfer functions). These properties come from the fact that Wave Digital Filters are derived by local discretization of circuit elements and their connections, a process which (when implemented properly) strictly ensures that the energetic properties of the analog reference circuit are replicated in the Wave Digital Filter. This is critical to the simulation and it has been verified that the discretization method as well as the sampling frequency at which the circuit is calculated are directly related to the stability of the system [8].

Adaptors are also an important feature of Wave Digital Filter, and the reflection free port must receive an important mention. Newer approaches introduce R type adaptors among other solutions that can be used to solve multiport nonlinearities [5]. One research trend is concerned with using a multidimensional generalisation of the Wave Digital Filter concept for the solution of Partial Differential Equations.

2.4 Black Box Modelling

2.4.1 Real-Time Modeling of Audio Distortion Circuits with Deep Learning

This article [11] looks into using deep neural networks to represent audio distortion circuits like distortion pedals and guitar amplifiers on a black-box basis. A recurrent neural network model and a feedforward network based on the WaveNet model are contrasted. Models of the Ibanez Tube Screamer, Boss DS-1, and Electro-Harmonix

Big MuffPi audio distortion pedals were made in order to find an appropriate hyperparameter configuration for the WaveNet. Three minutes of audio data are demonstrated to be adequate for training neural network models. The computational burden of the neural networks was assessed using real-time implementations. The Blackstar HT-5 Metal and Mesa Boogie 5:50 Plus valve amplifier models were built, and subjective testing were carried out, to further corroborate the findings. The results of the listening test indicate that the first amplifier’s models could be distinguished from the reference, but the top models were assessed to have good sound quality. Many listeners were unable to distinguish between the reference sound and the signals generated by the two biggest neural network models in the instance of the second guitar amplifier. This study shows that neural network models, some of which only need a tiny amount of processing power to function on a current desktop computer, can successfully replicate extremely nonlinear audio distortion circuits while operating in real-time.

Figure 2: Block diagram of a single convolutional layer [3].

Convolutional Layer

In Figure 2, the suggested model is displayed. The dilated causal FIR filter $H_k(z^{d_k})$, where k is the layer index and d_k is the integer-valued filter dilation factor, is used to first handle the input signal. Convolutional filtering is carried out as a multiple-input and multiple-output (MIMO) convolution with a kernel H_k since convolutional layers typically have multiple channels. In other words, a filter must be learned for every set of input and output channels. Impulse responses are present in the separate filters in the kernel.

$$h[n] = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} w_m \delta[n - md_k] \quad (2.11)$$

where w_m are the non-zero coefficients of the filters the network learnt, and $\delta[n]$ is the Kronecker delta function. The layer output is then created by applying a nonlinear activation function $f()$ to the biased convolution result.

$$z_k[n] = f[(H_k * x_k)[n] + b_k] \quad (2.12)$$

And the layer includes a residual connection that produces the resulting next layer

$$x_{k+1}[n] = W_k z_k[n] + x_k[n] \quad (2.13)$$

where the mixing between the layer input x_k and the layer output z_k prior to the next layer is controlled by the 11 convolution kernel W_k . A Wiener model, which consists of a linear filter followed by a static nonlinearity, can be used to describe each convolutional layer. The WaveNet-style neural network, which is a cascade of Wiener models, makes less assumptions about the design of the device being simulated, making it applicable to the modeling of a variety of nonlinear systems.

Receptive Field

Each output sample predicted by the causal feedforward WaveNet-style model depends only on the N prior input samples, where N is referred to as the model's receptive field. The number of convolutional layers and the lengths of the filters within those layers affect the receptive field. Generally the receptive field is given by

$$N = (M - 1) \sum_{k=1}^K d_k + 1 \quad (2.14)$$

K indicates how many convolutional layers there are. It is possible to raise the model order to thousands of samples with only a few layers by raising the dilation

by a factor of two. This enables feedforward modeling of systems with long impulse responses.

In earlier research, a three layer "post-processing module" with 1x1 convolutions and nonlinear activation functions was fed the outputs of the convolutional layers. A 1x1 convolution, as used in convolutional neural networks, is a matrix multiplication that is done to the signal at each time step. In this study, a linear mixer—a single linear 1x1 convolution layer—replaces the post-processing module. In accordance with our tests, the linear output layer improves network performance while lowering network complexity and computational burden.

Loss Function

By reducing the error to signal ratio (ESR) in relation to the training data, the neural network was trained. The output and target signals were subjected to a "pre-emphasis" filter during training and validation before the ESR was calculated. The pre-emphasized ESR for the i th training example is provided by

$$\mathcal{E}^i = \frac{\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} |y_p^i[n] - \hat{y}_p^i[n]|^2}{\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} |y_p^i[n]|^2} \quad (2.15)$$

where \hat{y}_p^i is the preemphasized neural network output and y_p^i is the preemphasized target signal. An energy-normalized sum-of-squares error is what the ESR is. Without energy normalization, the training data segments with the highest energy would account for the majority of the loss. The first-order highpass filter with transfer function

$$H(z) = 1 - 0.95z^{-1} \quad (2.16)$$

was selected as the pre-emphasis filter because is very commonly used in speech processing. Middle and high frequencies are highlighted in the loss function by the filtering.

Results and Conclusions

In this work the researchers were able to implement this methodology into different analog circuits including the tube screamer, and the results were successful. They found some issues with aliasing but stated the following sentence: "Although aliasing is evident with a high frequency sinusoidal input, no clear aliasing could be heard in the guitar and bass sounds processed through the models." In their conclusions researchers summed up the following: "A real-time and low-latency implementation of the proposed neural network was developed. The results suggest that the proposed deep learning approach can be used to train accurate digital models of analog distortion effects, which can be run in real-time on a consumer-grade desktop computer."

2.4.2 Real-Time Black-Box Modelling With Recurrent Neural Networks

The use of a recurrent neural network for the blackbox modeling of nonlinear audio systems, such as tube amplifiers and distortion pedals, is suggested in this research. Several minutes of guitar and bass recordings are used to train the neural networks after they have been played through the modeling devices. A JUCE framework has been used to create a real-time audio plugin that uses the networks. It is demonstrated that, although using substantially less processing resources, recurrent neural networks attain accuracy levels comparable to those of the WaveNet model. The proposed neural networks, in particular a Long Short Term Memory Recurrent Unit, represents a significant advancement in the precise and economical computer simulation of distortion and tube amplifiers.

Long Short Term Memory

The cell state c and the hidden state h are the two vectors that make up the unit's state in an LSTM. The initial cell state, $c[n1]$, the initial hidden state, $h[n1]$, and the current time step input, $x[n]$, serve as the inputs at each time step. The updated hidden state, $h[n]$, and the updated cell state, $c[n]$, are the LSTM's two outputs.

Figure 3: Diagram of an LSTM.

Figure 3 shows an LSTM unit. The following functions are used to obtain the outputs:

$$i[n] = \sigma(W_{ii}x[n] + b_{ii} + W_{hi}h[n-1] + b_{hi}) \quad (2.17)$$

$$f[n] = \sigma(W_{if}x[n] + b_{if} + W_{hf}h[n-1] + b_{hf}) \quad (2.18)$$

$$\tilde{c}[n] = \tanh(W_{ic}x[n] + b_{ic} + W_{hc}h[n-1] + b_{hc}) \quad (2.19)$$

$$o[n] = \sigma(W_{io}x[n] + b_{io} + W_{ho}h[n-1] + b_{ho}) \quad (2.20)$$

$$c[n] = f[n]c[n-1] + i[n]\tilde{c}[n] \quad (2.21)$$

$$h[n] = o[n] \tanh(c[n]) \quad (2.22)$$

where $\tanh(\cdot)$ is the hyperbolic tangent function and $\sigma(\cdot)$ is the logistic sigmoid function, and $i[n]$ is the input gate, $f[n]$ is the forget gate, $c[n]$ is the candidate cell state, $o[n]$ is the output gate.

The hidden state and the cell state make up the LSTM unit state. The eight

weight matrices and eight bias vectors, respectively indicated by W and b in the equations above, define the state update of the LSTM unit. The biases in the neural network are only continuous offsets imposed during the unit calculation, and they have nothing to do with bias in electronic circuits, it should be mentioned. The LSTM unit's learnable parameters, which are acquired during training, are made up of these weights and biases. The input size as well as the hidden size of the LSTM dictate the size of the weight matrices and bias vectors. The initial states for the following time step, $n + 1$, are the updated hidden state, $h[n]$, and the updated cell state, $c[n]$. Our model's fully connected layer receives the updated hidden state as an input for the current time step, n , from the LSTM.

Loss Function

The error-to-signal ratio (ESR) with pre-emphasis filtering provides the basis for the loss function employed during training, as described in [3] [12]. The ESR is calculated by dividing the squared error by the energy of the target signal. Before calculating the ESR, a pre-emphasis filter was applied to the output and target signals. The network learns to model the high-frequency material with the aid of the pre-emphasis filter. The pre-emphasized ESR for a training signal segment of length N is provided by:

$$\mathcal{E}_{ESR} = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} |y_p[n] - \hat{y}_p[n]|^2}{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} |y_p[n]|^2} \quad (2.23)$$

where \hat{y}_p is the output of the neural network pre-emphasized and y_p is the target signal. First-order high-pass filter with the following transfer function was chosen as the pre-emphasis filter.

$$H(z) = 1 - 0.95z^{-1} \quad (2.24)$$

To lessen the DC offset in the model outputs, a DC term was also added to the loss. The DC loss term is provided by:

$$\mathcal{E}_{DC} = \frac{|\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} y[n] - \hat{y}[n]|^2}{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} |y[n]|^2} \quad (2.25)$$

Early experiments revealed that the model outputs had a DC offset, leading to the introduction of the DC term. The following is the final loss function used for training:

$$\mathcal{E} = \mathcal{E}_{ESR} + \mathcal{E}_{DC} \quad (2.26)$$

Truncated Back-Propagation Through Time

It is possible to update the network parameters at each time step when training RNNs, but doing so has a large computational cost. Allowing the RNN to process a whole sequence before updating the parameters is an alternate strategy. Back-propagation Across Time (BPTT) is the term used to describe the process of finding the necessary gradients by back-propagating through the entire sequence [13]. Since the network parameters are only updated once per sequence when modeling extremely lengthy sequences, training becomes sluggish. Additionally, each update necessitates time-consuming computational back propagation through the whole sequence.

When processing a sequence, parameter changes are made using the truncated BPTT [14] technique. As a result, updates can happen frequently and the recurring unit state can survive changes. The user selects the training hyperparameters, which include the number of time steps to run BPTT through for each update and the frequency of parameter changes [15]. Since the model was trained on audio sampled at a rate of 44.1 kHz, even a second of audio has a very lengthy sequence. As a result, abbreviated BPTT was employed in this study's RNN training. As this was discovered to be an efficient update frequency during the first studies, the parameter modifications were carried out every 2048 samples, with BPTT being conducted across 2048 time steps each update.

Batch-Processing

The training dataset was divided into parts of half a second segments. On the one hand by breaking the dataset up into many discrete sequences, the short sequences may be analyzed simultaneously, drastically cutting down on processing time. On

the other hand, small segments make it possible to shuffle the dataset at each epoch, which is known to speed up network convergence [30]. At the start of each epoch, the training data segments were mixed together and processed in mini-batches of 40 segments. The starting state of the recurrent unit is set to 0 at the beginning of each mini-batch. In order to give the recurrent unit state time to initialize, the first 1000 samples are then processed without altering the network settings. After then, back-propagation and parameter adjustments are performed every 2048 samples while processing the remaining samples. Up until the training dataset is digested in its whole, this is repeated. After that, the training dataset is randomized for the subsequent training period.

Real-time implementation

In C++, a real-time RNN implementation was created. The JUCE framework and the Eigen library were used to build the implementation, which supports matrix and vector operations. Real-time audio plugins in the prevalent VST, AU, and AAX formats used by contemporary digital audio workstations may be created using JUCE. The created plugin enables audio processing using the learned models.

Conclusions

Compared to a WaveNet-like convolutional neural network that was previously described, the single layer RNN model shown in this article uses significantly less processing resources and can operate in real time. Depending on the device being modelled, the RNN model's accuracy was also on par with or even superior to that of the WaveNet. This work allows for model generation and the real-time implementation allows for plugin generation conveniently.

Chapter 3

Methods

This section consists in the explanation of all the procedures that have been carried out during this project. First a comprehensive description of the used analog circuit, including the linear and nonlinear parts as well as the clone circuit construction. Once the circuit is completed and tested, a dataset using the input and output signals coming from it is generated in order to be able to train the Neural Network. An explanation of the dataset, the soundcard connection, the Neural Network training, the parameters used as well as an explanation of how the real-time plugin was obtained follows. Finally the metrics to evaluate the resulting simulation are introduced.

3.1 Circuit description

The case study circuit is a clone of the Ibanez TS808 Tube Screamer, a few differences with the original circuit is that it has FET switching and buffered bypass, while the clone in use has only a true bypass switching, as it can be argued that this part is not affecting the sound. The clone retains the original BJT input and output buffers [1]. This circuit is structured as a distortion and an amplifier in cascade configuration. In figure 1 we can see the schematic that has been constructed. It has two potentiometers that control the amount of distortion and the output volume respectively.

3.1.1 Distortion

This first part is considered a distortion circuit as the output signal doesn't follow a linear transformation when compared to the original input signal.

The V_{ref} connected to the $10k\Omega$ resistor allows for the operational amplifier to be powered by V_{cc} on the positive power supply and $0V$ or ground on the negative power supply, so the input signal is centered at V_{ref} . V_{ref} is half the value of V_{cc} , which is $9V$, so V_{ref} equals $4V5$.

The signal is fed forward to the positive input of the operational amplifier TL072 and amplified according to the value of the R_{drive} linear potentiometer, the antiparallel diodes are arranged in a way that produces soft clipping, as each limit the amount of voltage at the output both at a high and a low boundary. The greater the value for R_{drive} the more amplified is the signal thus more distortion is produced, as a greater part of the signal is affected by the diodes' voltage limitation.

This produces a nonlinearity, as we could imagine in an extreme case the output signal for a sinusoid would resemble a quadratic waveform, creating new harmonics not present in the original signal. This is the most complex part to simulate and we will later discuss different manners it can be tackled.

3.1.2 Volume Gain

The in cascade following circuit represents a gain stage, which can be understood as a simple volume amplifier. The volume at the output is controlled by the second potentiometer and allows for volume gain control of the distorted signal. This circuit is linear and the simulation should be fairly easy to implement as long as there is no clipping of the operational amplifier (which will not be our study case).

3.1.3 Circuit Construction

To obtain a ground truth for the simulation comparison I built the circuit using silicon components. In addition, to be able to interact with the circuit and be able

to measure all the important voltages and resistor values I added a series of terminals for that purpose. In this circuit I am able to measure the input and output signal using a 6mm jack connector, the voltage and current value of the V_{cc} and V_{ref} as well as the resistor values of both potentiometers.

The main active component of this circuit is the operational amplifier TL072, a high speed JFET input single operational amplifier with low noise versions and a high slew rate. In addition, the output bias and offset currents are both modest. It has two op-amps on board, also referred to as dual Op-amp IC. The TL072 series has minimal harmonic distortion and noise, making it ideal for high precision audio applications [2].

The rest of the components used, which are passive, are a series of resistors, capacitors, two diodes (that form the nonlinearity), two potentiometers, a led, a 9V battery and a switch, along the connectors. The circuit is firmly fastened in an acrylic case and to use the circuit an input 6mm connector goes into the left connector and the output into the right connector, the battery has to be connected, and the switch turned on, producing a red light by the led. Depending on which position the potentiometers are set, the output signal is going to be affected by the distortion (left potentiometer) and volume (right potentiometer). In further lines the connection to the audio interface will be explained thoroughly.

To check the correctness of the circuit various tests have been performed in order to validate the distortion and the frequency response. First a test sinusoid at 1kHz is both recorded and inputted into the circuit so that it can be then compared with the also recorded audio signal at the output. Then a similar setup is performed but this time a test sine swipe (up to 20kHz) is input and the output is recorded in order to obtain the frequency response of the circuit.

As stated beforehand the TL072 has a modest output power and the lack of power stages, present in the original device, results in coupling and oscillating when an electronic instrument is connected to the input, so only line-type devices, for instance a sound card, can be used to obtain a correct output. A picture of the actual Tube

Screamer clone can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Tube Screamer clone built.

3.2 NN Simulation

3.2.1 Dataset

Once I have created and checked the correct functioning of the tube screamer clone I am able to generate a dataset in order to be able to train a model of it, using pedalnet software¹. The dataset generated includes both the input as well as the output waveforms going in and coming out of the analog Tube Screamer circuit, and follow a series of technical characteristics stated by the creators in their repository: The waveforms need to be .wav files as well as single channel, 44.1 kHz, FP32 data (not int16). The files should be 3 - 4 minutes long, and contain a variety of chords, individual notes, and different playing techniques to get a full spectrum of data for

¹<https://github.com/GuitarML/pedalnet>

the model to "learn" from.

In my particular case I have used my electric guitar, a Cort strat style with Seymour Duncan Hot Rodded Humbucker Set SH4 y SH2, neck pickup in humbucker mode with max tone and volume, and the Tube Screamer set to full distortion and volume, which according to the creators of this software "the more distorted the effect/amp, the more difficult it is to train". For this reason I have created a dataset of almost 13 minutes for both the dry and the wet signal. The recording of this dataset has been done using a Motu M2 sound card with both input channels recording at the same time at 44.1kHz and 16 bits, using a DAW, Logic Pro X ² and then converted to FP32 using Reaper ³. To obtain a balanced dataset, the volumes of the clean guitar as well as the output of the TS had to be matched in terms of loudness, the built in volume regulators of each channel of the sound card were convenient to achieve that. All the code and scripts used can be found in one place ⁴.

3.2.2 Training and parameters

The model was trained using the script provided *train.py*. This function is written in pytorch and the training took 48 hours to complete using a Macbook air M1 after having arranged the input and output files using the *prepare_data.py* functionality. Some adjustments had to be set up as well as the paths to the convenient directories.

The parameters to train the neural network are set to the following values:

--num_channels

The number of channels in the recurrent neural network. In this particular case is set to 16.

--dilation_depth

The amount of hidden layers for each sample. In this particular case is set to 8.

²<https://www.apple.com/logic-pro/>

³<https://www.reaper.fm/>

⁴<https://github.com/miquel-royo>

--num_repeat

The amount of repetitions. In this particular case is set to 3.

--kernel_size

The size of the feature extraction for each step. In this particular case is set to 3.

--batch_size

The number of training samples in one forward/backward pass. In this particular case is set to 32.

--learning_rate

The amount that the weights are updated during training. In this particular case is set to 3e-3.

--max_epochs

Represents the training of the neural network with all the training data for one cycle. In an epoch, we use all of the data exactly once. A forward pass and a backward pass together are counted as one pass. In this particular case is set to 58.

--gpus

Represents the amount of GPUs we can use to train the model. In my particular case I am using a M1 Macbook air, so this parameter is set to 0.

3.2.3 Real-time plugin generation

Once the model has been generated I used the software provided by the people at GuitarML ⁵ called WaveNetVA to produce a real-time plugin that can be used in the vast majority of DAWs.

⁵<https://github.com/GuitarML/WaveNetVA>

First it was required to convert the model from Pedalnet to WaveNetVA format, which was performed using the function "convert_pedalnet_to_wavenetva.py" provided in the Pedalnet repository. In a nutshell this function rearranges the weights from the Pedalnet model with the WaveNetVA fashion. The WaveNetVA software allows to convert any model into a VST which can be converted to a .component and loaded into Logic Pro X and perform in real time, obtaining similar results than using the original tube screamer clone. This plugin also allows for user control parameters, the user can select the position of two knobs, one for pre-gain of the signal to be transformed and a post-gain to regulate the amount of loudness of the signal after the effect has been applied, making it similar in looks to the analog clone, as seen in figure 4. It also allows for model selection as this software includes various already trained models including one of a TS9 Tube Screamer.

3.3 Evaluation methods

Using the functionalities provided by the pedalnet software, the error to signal ratio value is obtained and a residual spectrogram is plotted to perform an evaluation of the simulation.

Figure 5: User interface provided by WaveNet as seen in Logic Pro X.

Chapter 4

Results

4.1 ESR

Using the functionalities the pedalnet software provides we can obtain a series of metrics to evaluate the model accuracy. Using the function *test.py* we generate three elements, a predicted short fragment and the corresponding input and output fragments of the training dataset. In order to obtain the value for the error to signal ratio (ESR), defined by equation 2.25, we use the function *plot_wav.py* and we get an ESR of 0.1455.

4.2 Spectral analysis

The same *plot_wav.py* provides a residual spectrogram (the resulting when subtracting the predicted to the training output). Notice that the highest values in figure 6 are around -50dB.

Figure 6: Residual spectrogram.

Chapter 5

Discussion

The main goal of this project was to serve the student as an introduction into neural networks. This was achieved by simulating analog circuits and paying attention at every step in the process to achieve that, due to the prior knowledge on electronic circuits. In the following discussion a series of points of view will be discussed and finally a set of conclusions will shed some light on the approach followed and how the results obtained have helped the student obtain the goals pursued.

5.1 Discussion

The Tube Screamer clone sound is very harsh, dirty and fat as it has been set to the max distortion it allows. More noise is present on the sound, compared to the simulation. In terms of equalization the bass is accentuated, the mids are excessively amplified and the treble sounds can not be heard.

On the other hand the sound of the waveNet plugin is more subtle, even if set at maximum distortion by setting the pre amp knob present in the interface. Sound is more clear and melodies can be perceived better than with the clone. In terms of equalization bass is more defined, mids are not overamplified and treble sounds can be heard clearly. This could be due to the fact that no real band-pass filter has been applied to this approach thus higher frequencies are not removed so drastically.

The neural network used was not designed nor constructed by the student, nor was the plugin generator, although many parameters and training choices have been fine tuned in order to obtain the shown results.

5.2 Conclusions

The obtained results in terms of simulation are positive as a real-time with user controls plugin has been generated and can be used in the vast majority of digital audio workstations, which is also a great goal in terms of practicality and usefulness of the project results. The obtained ESR and the residual spectrogram represent a solid result concerning the accuracy.

In respect of the effect obtained is not exactly true to the original training audios but it sounds definitely like a tube screamer with less noise and a more balanced equalization.

The results with reference to allowing the student to get into neural networks has been productive as it has allowed to fine tune particular aspects of the system. Besides it has allowed the student to grasp some insights on the topic and feel more comfortable when using this new approach. The initial idea to use electronic circuits as the basis has proved to be the right approach.

For future work could be interesting to dive deeper in the fine tuning of all the parameters present in the neural network in order to obtain an even better metrics, or even use the learned knowledge to tackle other types of circuits using a similar approach.

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Appendix A

Plotted signal comparison

Figure 7: Plot signal comparison.

Appendix B

Detailed signal comparison

Figure 8: Plot detail signal comparison.

Appendix C

Tube Screamer spectrum

Figure 9: Plot Tube Screamer clone spectrum.

Appendix D

WaveNet spectrum

Figure 10: Plot WaveNet spectrum.

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